

NUTRI-KNOW

Farmer's Encyclopedia on innovative Nutrient Management Solutions

EIP-AGRI Operational Group Struvite

Activity

The environmental sustainability of the Struvite has been estimated using the LCA - Life Cycle Assessment methodology.

The LCA analysis evaluated the Carbon Footprint expressed in kg of CO₂ eq/m³ of slurry, comparing the innovative effluent management (treatment) and existing livestock slurry management (control).

The greenhouse gas emissions have been estimated from storage of the dense fraction and supernatant for the treatment thesis and the liquid fraction leaving the separator for the control thesis.

Furthermore, emissions from the production of materials, reagents and energy for prototype operation have been included in the treatment thesis, as well as the environmental benefit from applying renewable fertilizer.

Further details

Total budget: € 185.819,96

Total financed: € 171.715,06

Main funding source: Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups

Rural Development Programme: 2014IT06RDRP003 Italy - Rural Development Programme (Regional) - Emilia-Romagna

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Emilia-Romagna, Italy

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Struvite

Struvite environmental sustainability

Objectives

The goal of the Struvite Operational Group was to decrease the nitrogen and phosphorus content in pig digestate in order to reduce ammonia, methane and nitrous oxide emissions from storage, ammonia and nitrous oxide emissions from spreading. The nitrogen and phosphorus recovered produce struvite (a renewable, slow-release fertilizer product consisting of ammonium, phosphorus, and magnesium in a stable crystalline form) that can replace chemical fertilizers in nutrient-deficient areas and promote the nutrient balance in high livestock areas characterized by nutrient surplus.

Results of the Carbon Footprint of innovative effluent management (treatment) compared to traditional management (control) and contribution of individual items to the total

Results

The results of the Carbon Footprint report a greater contribution to climate change from traditional manure management than the innovation proposed by OG Struvite (27,7 kg CO₂ eq/m³ slurry of the control compared to 18,5 kg CO₂ eq/m³ slurry of the treatment).

The lower impact of the treatment compared to the control is due to the lower emission of methane and nitrous oxide from the storage phase due to the lower content of nitrogen and volatile solids of the stored matrices and the acidification of the thickened fraction.

The production of renewable fertilizer ensures a reduction in CO₂ emissions equivalent to 2 kg CO₂ eq/m³ slurry.

Methane emitted from the storage phase is the largest contributor to system emissions in both cases.

Electricity and reagents to power the prototype have a marginal impact on the total carbon footprint.

Context

Animal manure is an excellent fertilizer matrix for crops and soils as it is rich in both macro and micronutrients and organic matter, which are useful for agricultural soils. The downside is the ammonia and greenhouse gases emission from slurry or digestate during storage and spreading. In fact, the Italian agricultural sector determines about 7% of national GHG emissions, and of this share 19% comes from manure management.

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

As for ammonia emissions, the agricultural sector accounts for 94% of national emissions with 49.9% of that share coming from manure management (ISPRA, Reports 318/2020 and 319/2020).

Digestate from biogas plants must be stored and applied to crops when there is a need for its excellent content of plant nutrients. However, the downside is the high emissions potential from the liquid digestate during the storage phase. Ammonia emissions are high because there is a significant amount of nitrogen in ammonia form in the digestate and greenhouse gases (methane) are emitted due to the high organic matter content, even if it is less than in not digested slurry.

In Po Valley there is a high presence of livestock farms with biogas plant and so an optimal management of manure and digestates could result in reduced emissions.

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